

Using outcrop digital models to guide subsurface studies for CO₂ storage: An example from the Amellago Oolitic Ramp (Morocco) as an analogue for the Paris Basin Dogger Reservoir

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Key words: Subsurface analogue, Sequence stratigraphy, Jurassic, Morocco, Oolitic system, CCS

Understanding subsurface reservoirs remains an important objective for the future when considering carbon capture and storage (CCS) solutions for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. As with traditional subsurface studies, methods and techniques to characterise reservoirs for CCS are the same; utilising cores, well logs and/or seismic data, overseen by conceptual geological model. However, the lack of data for characterising geobodies, at the core of the reservoir, oblige geologists to use outcrop analogues. Furthermore, with the objective of having a true analogy, seismic-scale outcrop analogues are preferred (PLAYTON et al., 2010). One of the main problems of these objects is limited accessibility and it remains a challenge for the full assessment of outcrop analysis. The development of drone technologies in recent decades, followed by the improvement of image processing, photogrammetry, and software interpretations, allows us to remove the issue of outcrop accessibility and enables the accurate determination of the 3D architecture of seismic-scale outcrops. Here we present a high resolution integrated interpretation of a 15km long UAV-based digital outcrop model (DOM) of the Amellago Limestone (Jurassic, High Atlas Morocco), with the objective to accurately understand the Dogger Formation of the Paris Basin, a principal target for CO₂ storage.

The Amellago cliffs are considered a world-class reference outcrop for oolitic carbonate ramp systems with a seismic-scale, continuous and structurally undeformed geometry (Figure 1). This Lower to Middle Jurassic ooid-dominated ramp system is exposed along a 37 km long series of steep cliffs which allow reliable geological interpretation. A drone-based photogrammetric acquisition was performed in 2018 with a novel workflow, integrating self-developed and commercial (UGCS) software solutions to obtain automatised, efficient, and accurate vertical flight paths with an UAV quadcopter (DJI Phantom 4 pro) (DUJONCQUOY et al., 2019). The model has been anchored with 33 ground control points and then generated from 21000 photos with the Agisoft Metashape Professional software. The digital outcrop model has a 1.54 cm/pix resolution and has been interpreted with the Virtual Reality Geological Studio software (Fig 1). The geological interpretation of the model was initially based on a (field-based) pre-existing interpretation (PIERRE et al., 2010) in order to guide the determination of the stratigraphic framework at large scale. Subsequently, “seismic” sequence stratigraphy principles were applied to identify bedding surface terminations as toplap, downlap or onlap to understand the true internal architecture.

Figure 1: Third order sequence mapping along the km long photogrammetric model of the Amellago limestone.

In this study, the work concentrated on the sequence Am4, one of the nine 3rd order stratigraphic sequences; described in the literature within the area of interest (Pierre et al., 2010). The latter is limited by major maximum regressive surfaces (MRS) defined from the distal part of the sedimentary system and tracked inwards along the DOM. Transgressive and regressive intervals were defined based on the identification of major maximum flooding intervals, characterised by massive recessive intervals. Thickness variations and stratigraphy on the proximal-distal profile were quantified by serial digital logs, which have been calibrated to fieldwork data. The regressive stages show a thickening outward (20m) and slightly inclined geometries (0.1°) while the transgressive stage is tabular. Eleven HF cycles are identified in the sequence Am4. These cycles are bounded by higher frequency MRS. Even if these HF cycles seem relatively tabular at large scale, they show complex internal architecture with onlap, toplap and downlap surface geometry terminations. The detailed mapping of the surfaces and internal geometries resulted in the identification of sequence stratigraphic motifs associated to retrogradation, aggradation-progradation and pure-progradation prism. These motifs are faciologically calibrated by field observations, sampling and existing literature. Finally, detailed sedimentological observations made of individual geobodies allow us to partition and classify oolitic dunes along different sequence stratigraphic motifs and propose an accurate facies model along this oolitic ramp. A systematic analysis of these objects showed a variety of dune characteristics (extension, thickness, stacking, contact, dip etc.) on a proximal-distal profile. The proximal part is composed of multiple kilometre wide shoal complexes with successive thin (3m) and wide (>1km) dunes, present along both retrograding and aggrading-prograding prism. In contrast oolitic dunes from the distal part are isolated, thicker (5m), poorly extended (<100m) and only distributed at the top of aggrading-prograding and pure-progradation prisms.

All results obtained from the interpretation of the Amellago outcrop model have been used for a subsurface CO₂ storage reservoir characterisation in the Paris Basin. Owing to a large and unique dataset for CO₂ storage assessment, such as newly acquired 3D seismic data, well logs and cores, a complete reservoir characterisation was possible. However, the lack of intermediate scale resolution associated with oolitic dunes, oblige us to use results and concepts developed on the Amellago study. After a comparison of sedimentary facies, stacking patterns (facies and sequence) and general sequence stratigraphic architecture, we identify some similarities between the Dogger Platform and Amellago Cliff. Results obtained can guide us to target specific seismic sub-units and drive specific static modelling for an accurate CO₂ injection.

In conclusion, the Amellago case study provides a good example of how highly detailed photogrammetric acquisitions and interpretations of seismic-scale outcrop analogues can enable access to accurate reconstructions of stratal framework and associated facies partitioning, which can be directly applied for subsurface characterisation. The next objective of this study will be to integrate results from hyperspectral scanning (DUJONCQUOY *et al.*, submitted), showing diagenetic reservoir intervals, in order to generate forward modelling for an immediate application during subsurface reservoir modelling.

Acknowledgements: Author and co-authors would like to thank TotalEnergies and specifically the PIT (Projet d'Innovation Technologique) for project funding.

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